

Deploying data spaces infrastructure for secure and resilient digital twins towards automated rail transport planning and operation

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ABSTRACT

Presently the railway is the most used means of transport, and as such there is a need to digitalize and automate rail planning and operation. The automation of rail operations requires large amounts of data, but most industry stakeholders are reluctant to share data. Moreover, sensor data is being collected, although the processing and exploitation of these data are faced with legal, economic, or technical setbacks. This has necessitated the development of decentralized data ecosystems such as “data spaces” which provide a solution for trusted data sharing through dedicated connectors that enables reliable and secure data hub. Accordingly, this article discusses how the Federated Rail Data Space (RDS) implemented as part of Europe's Rail FP1 MOTIONAL project is leveraged for developing digital twin data representation of rail operations. Furthermore, RDS incorporates trusted data exchange, ensuring transparency and accountability among stakeholders, e.g., manufacturers, suppliers, assets and infrastructure managers. The findings present an architectural concept that shows how data space connectors support reliable and secure data sharing for digital twins of rail assets. Overall, the RDS enables the development of digital twin models that use data in real time for rail planning and operations. The RDS offers technological building blocks for the rail twin transition.

1. Introduction

The planning, design, and operation of public transport services such as railway infrastructure are important for achieving sustainable public transportation. Over the years, Digital Twins (DTs) have been deployed across different sectors such as in architecture, engineering, design, and transportation domains (Otsu & Maso, 2024). A DT is a virtual replica of a physical entity. It connects the physical and the digital world using data seamlessly transmitted, enabling the digital entity to exist simultaneously with the physical entity (El Saddik, 2018), making it possible to change one entity without changing the other (Nativi et al., 2021). A DT typically comprises of three main elements: physical entity, digital model, and the connection between both entities that supports automated data exchange between the physical and the digital entities (Nativi et al., 2021). In DTs the digital replicas of physical entities, procedures, or systems integrate data from different sources, including Internet of Things (IoT) devices, to model or simulate existing railway environments and their infrastructural dynamics (Khatiwada et al., 2026; Schinke & Roßmann, 2024).

The capabilities of DT facilitate Intelligent rail planning and

operational services, such as simulation, controlling, prediction, monitoring, etc. (Somma et al., 2023), to support asset management for rail infrastructure. Although, data is one of the constituents needed to develop DTs that facilitate automated rail planning and operation, stakeholders in the railway industry such as asset managers and infrastructure managers are faced with data management issues (Schinke & Roßmann, 2024). Moreover, the implementation of secure and resilient DT requires railway stakeholders to have data sovereignty, data ownership, and data security (Moreno et al., 2023). Similarly, there is a need for data availability, the provision of cost-efficient, and scalable data storage. This requires the option to store data asset in a cloud environment where it can be processed over its whole lifetime (Stojanovic et al., 2021), to foster the development of scalable DT across the railway sector. However, existing DT systems are connected to traditional centralized data storage solutions. Consequently, resulting to fragmented data ecosystem, following closed proprietary vendor locked solutions that hinder the evolution of innovative business. This is also limited by the lack of well-established interoperable open solutions (Solmaz et al., 2022).

Thus, there is need to deploy an infrastructure that enables the

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development and management of data-driven services and aim to combat siloed data storage and usage. As such, the concept of data spaces has been introduced as a solution to integrate these disparate data sources, providing an alternative to centralized structured data storage (Franklin et al., 2005). Accordingly, this current study proposes to employ “data space” which are federated data ecosystems that enable participants to efficiently, access data securely and transparently in a trustworthy manner within a specific domain. Due to the potential of data space this technology is now gaining traction across different sectors such as in the mobility (<https://mobility-dataspace.eu/>) and is being deployed for data management by creating a data ecosystem where mobility stakeholders can participate contribute and share and or exchange data (Gao, 2024; Martella et al., 2023). Data spaces are appropriate for managing digital modeling related to data flow, as in the case of DTs (Martella et al., 2023).

Data spaces can significantly enhance the proficiency of Rail DTs by improving data integration, interoperability, analysis, and decision-making (Schinke & Roßmann, 2024), for supporting the operation of public rail operations (both for metro or long-distance) for mobility of passenger and freight services. For example, mobility service providers and railway operators may use data within the data space to carry out demand forecasting, optimization of rail processes, optimal traffic management, predictive maintenance of assets, quality control, anomaly detection, and real time decision-making support (Martella et al., 2023; Schinke & Roßmann, 2024). Therefore, this article aims to address the following research question.

- How can data spaces enable data sharing for secure and resilient digital twins for automated rail planning and operation?

Therefore, as part of Europe's Rail FP1 MOTIONAL project this study discusses how the federated Rail Data Space (RDS) supports trusted, secure, and reliable data transfer and integration from IoT devices ensuring that digital twins can promote asset management towards a resilient rail twin transition. Evidence from this study proposes an architectural concept that serves as a technological building block for high-quality and effective digital model implementations to support advanced rail planning and operational processes. The architectural concept offers a secure, consistent, and trusted data ecosystem for automated rail planning and operation. The remainder of this article is organized as follows: Section 2 outline the methods employed. Then the main findings are presented in Section 3. Finally, the conclusion is presented in Section 4.

2. Methods

This study employs a systematic mapping method to review existing literature related to the study area of data spaces for digital twins in rail planning and operations. Systematic mapping as a research approach aims to derive value for knowledge aggregation and is employed to gain an extensive understanding of a study area (Kitchenham & Charters, 2007). Systematic mapping helps to uncover trends, patterns, and identify key issues, research gaps and future research directions within a domain (Budgen et al., 2008). Based on systematic mapping this study was carried out in different phases, including defining research question (s), objectives and aims, carrying out searches and refining keywords, screening selected articles, and finally data extraction and presentation (Sonnenberg & Vom Brocke, 2012). The literature search was carried out in Google Scholar using the following keywords "data space" and "digital twins" and "rail" and "planning" and "operation". The search scope includes sources addressing data spaces in digital twins resulting in 48 articles which were read after which qualitative data was extracted from these sources.

3. Findings

3.1. Digital twins for resilient rail infrastructure

In such a changing and demanding public transport sector, railway operators and infrastructure managers are challenged to explore novel data-driven systems capable of promoting resilient rail services. Resilience can be defined as the ability to resist challenging situations. In the context of the railway sector a resilient system refers to the capability of these systems to absorb and withstand disruptions and quickly recover to perform intended tasks. For effective railway transport there is a need for the existing infrastructure to resiliently operate in different environments (Alexopoulos et al., 2023). Among the essential characteristics of a resilient system are the ability to monitor critical development and to anticipate future threats (Hollnangel et al., 2006), both abilities can be promisingly supported by Digital Twins technology.

As stated by the Digital Twin Consortium a DT is simply a digital representation of physical (real-world) entities and processes, synchronized at a specified fidelity and frequency (Azzedin et al., 2026; Raihan, 2026; Stojanovic et al., 2021). These physical assets are typically equipped with IoT devices such as sensors, metering devices, cameras, etc. integrated to collect real time data on the physical entity transmitted (Gao, 2024; Kumar et al., 2026). These data are transmitted through secure communication between the physical assets represented as digital representations throughout the asset's lifecycle (Gao, 2024; Moreno et al., 2023). The physical state of the asset can be replicated and represented in a simulated environment as a virtual model that integrates data. The data ranges from different sources such as sensor measurements, Computer-aided design (CAD) models, historical performance data, operating conditions of the physical asset, etc. (Alhazmi et al., 2025; Gao, 2024). The features of DT applicable for the railway sector are summarized in Table 1 (Stojanovic et al., 2021).

Table 1 summarizes a few features of DT which make it suitable for rail planning and operation. In the railway sector DT enables seamless connection between the physical assets (e.g. bridges, stations, etc.), and digital representation of the asset. It enables two-way mapping and integration of sensor data from physical assets to support in optimization and maintenance of rail infrastructure (Gao, 2024; Moreno et al., 2023). DT facilitates data exchange for information modeling, simulation, and real time monitoring of rail systems, providing valuable insights to asset managers for improving smart planning and operations without disrupting rail transport services (Gao, 2024; Labib, 2025). This enables generating mockups of what-if scenarios, prediction of outcomes, and response of appropriate preemptive actions, thereby assisting asset managers in making informed decisions related to infrastructure planning and management (Martella et al., 2023).

Table 1
Features of DT applicable for the railway sector.

Features	Description
Bi-directional connectivity	DT enables bi-directional connection for the asset or infrastructure attributes, via standardized communication protocols, such as OPC UA (Open Platform Communications - Unified Architecture). MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport), etc.
Data translation	DT supports data translation via the internal DT data model including semantic and syntax adaptation.
Interactive interface	DT provides interactive representational state transfer (REST)-application programming interface (API) interfaces for actors such as railway operators, infrastructure and asset managers.
Real time data	DT provides real time data stored in internal and external databases based on physical assets.
Model integration	DT provides execution environments to execute digital models such as physical models, data-driven, physic based, etc.
Promote data security	DT supports data security measures such as usage control authorization and authentication.

Additionally, the data collected can be used to track the performance of rail infrastructure thereby helping asset managers to predict changes in rail assets and forecast potential future actions by responding quickly to issues that may disrupt rail transport services (Gao, 2024). However, the use of data from IoT devices and from other sources is faced with data sovereignty and ownership challenges. This necessitates the need to implement new tools that enable both data owners and data-services providers to define data usage policies applicable throughout the data lifecycle (Moreno et al., 2023). Thus, this study aims at deploying a data space that enables data owners and data producers to define policies needed for integrating digital twins and move towards secure and resilient rail planning and operation.

3.2. Data space for exchange of rail infrastructure data

To ensure safe data exchange there is a need to ensure that data owners can define usage policies rules for data shared aimed at safeguarding their self-sovereignty, ownership, and autonomy in accordance with legally agreed usage contracts (Martella et al., 2025). As such “data space” is proposed, where a data space is a level of abstraction that provides a collection of data sources, services and devices within one space (Franklin et al., 2005). These data sources may be physically distributed but are offered through a single entity via the data space, making it easier for participants to access and use the data, while data remains at their source. Accordingly, the EU initiative GAIA-X (2022) defined data spaces as virtual data integration approach. Additionally, data space offers a trusted ecosystem involving multiple participants that supports sovereign and secure exchange of data (Alexopoulos et al., 2023). The main goals of data spaces related to data sharing are seen in Fig. 1.

From an institutional perspective, data spaces involve decentralized collaboration between organizations that have mutual goals of data sharing based on technical infrastructure and governance framework (Anthony, 2025; Bokolo, 2025). In the data spaces participants contribute resources, capabilities, and co-operate without any central authority (Guggenberger et al., 2025). Using the data space infrastructure participants exchange data for domain specific use cases based on pre-defined roles, responsibilities and governance rules (policies) of the data space (Guggenberger et al., 2025; Jnr & Sarshar, 2025). One of the most well-known data spaces initiatives driven in the EU comprises of the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), The Data Spaces Business Alliance (DSBA), Gaia-X, EOSC, and FIWARE that implement trusted data driven ecosystems on how their data are shared (Alexopoulos et al., 2023; Otto et al., 2019). These EU based initiatives employ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles which analyze and use diverse data from different sources and formats to improve data collection and access while promoting interoperable and sovereign data sharing (Hutterer & Krummy 2024).

In the context of this study data sharing between stakeholders in the railway sector requires both interoperability, security, and data sovereignty. Data spaces is a useful technology for asset and infrastructure management in the railway sector as it provides the infrastructure needed for supporting secure data sharing at a lower cost (Guggenberger et al., 2025; Jnr & Sarshar, 2025). Data spaces can offer resilience and secure rail transport services enabled by a clear set of usage policies (Gan et al., 2021), well-defined governance architecture, and communication protocol(s) for interface interconnectivity between the participants (e.g. railway operators, infrastructure managers, suppliers, manufacturers, etc.), within the data sharing ecosystem (Vogt et al., 2024).

3.3. Data spaces for secure and resilient integration of digital twins

In relation to rail planning and operations data spaces support real time data exchange for feeding with DT. Data spaces provide a dynamic environment for collecting, processing, integrating, and sharing of data

from different sources, such as IoT sensors, needed to represent the virtual model of physical rail infrastructures. DT enables predictive analytics, facilitating railway operators to anticipate challenges like traffic management, resource shortages, or inconsistencies in time-tabling (Phonsitthangkun et al., 2025). By continuous processing of real time data in a feedback loop DT enhance the effectiveness of rail transport planning and operational strategies (Schinke & Roßmann, 2024). Data spaces, by supplying secure, trusted data to DT enable the development of resilient DT that utilize these real time data from the physical assets enabling pervasive updates and feedback (Anthony Jnr et al., 2021; Schinke & Roßmann, 2024).

The collaborative data exchange approach fostered by data space enhances the richness, trustworthiness, and quality of data available for DTs, enabling more comprehensive analyses and better-informed decisions (Schinke & Roßmann, 2024). Furthermore, to effectively and efficiently support data sharing for DTs employed for rail planning and operations within the rail sector, there are key requirements that must be addressed such as trustworthiness, data sovereignty, openness, cross-domain collaboration, and FAIRness,¹ requirements not satisfied in existing implementations (Martella et al., 2025). The key requirements of data spaces for secure and resilient DTs within the railway sector are presented in Table 2.

3.4. Data space architectural concept implementation

By focusing on the requirements presented in Table 2 it is possible for the railway sector to develop a sustainable DT ecosystem connected to data space as support technology that helps asset managers to reduce costs, increase efficiency, and create innovative workflow. Data spaces employ open-source and standard building blocks essential for creating flexible, scalable, and resilient DT solutions (Martella et al., 2025; Hummel et al., 2021). The integration of data spaces to DTs ensures data security, sovereignty, and ownership when data is exchanged between stakeholders using DT for rail planning and operation of rail infrastructures. Therefore, Fig. 2 shows the data space architectural concept for secure and resilient digital twin highlighting how real time data collected from IoT sensors and devices installed on the physical assets from (data owners and/or data producers) are shared with (data consumers and/or data users).

Fig. 2 depicts a flow of real time data from the physical asset to the digital asset (digital twin) and vice versa. Real time data combined with historical and “domain-expert knowledge” are utilized to develop digital twins of an asset (Somma et al., 2023). Data spaces consist of different components such as connectors, vocabulary providers, identity providers, clearing house, meta data broker, and app store (Bokolo, 2025). The work from this article will only underline the applicability of the data space “connectors” as seen in Fig. 2. The connectors are software components that facilitate secure connection and communication between different stakeholders and other infrastructure within the data space. Thus, using connectors, the federated rail data space enables secure, trusted, reliable data exchange used to develop digital twin replica of modelled asset for the rail twin transition. The data space enables bidirectional interconnections with multiple data sources and data sinks, including digital twins.

The connectors support FAIR policies to ensure authenticity, trustworthiness, and provenance of data. Also, using data access mechanisms and usage control policies, the connectors promote data sovereignty, data security and privacy ensuring that data is exchanged with different stakeholders are in compliance with confidentiality, integrity, availability, and principles (Martella et al., 2023). The connectors provide access to all assets (real time data), enable data exchange via policies set by data owners/data producers that govern data exchange specifying

¹ FAIR data refers to data that has characteristics of being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

Fig. 1. Main goals of data spaces related to data sharing.

Table 2
Key requirements of data spaces for secure and resilient digital twins.

Requirement	Description
Trustworthiness	Data spaces provide a unified framework for defining robust legal mechanism that support trust and secure data exchange sharing needed to develop DTs used by participants.
Data sovereignty	Data spaces aim to ensure that data owners/data producers have autonomy and ownership of the shared data or exchanged data using by DT by providing defined schemes for enforcing legally binding data access and usage policies.
Data Interoperability	Data spaces provide data models and standards that can be deployed to exchange data via APIs for facilitating data sharing exchange between DTs.
Openness	Data spaces employ open-standard and are implemented based on open source such as the Eclipse Dataspace Connector for open data sharing with different DTs.
Cross-platform collaboration	Data spaces promote data sharing among different systems using different DT across the railway sector enabling data value creation.
FAIRness	The FAIR principles ensure that dataset produced from different sectors can be easily exchanged shared, reused, and integrated within different digital systems and organizations. Based on FAIR principles data spaces enhance accessibility, discoverability, and usability of data suitable for DTs.

how data is to be used. It also manages offers made on assets based on contractual agreements and finalized data transfer from external data sources to data sink. For examples this creates secure and reliable channel of communication between rail operators and asset managers.

3.5. Formal architectural specification

The data space connector in the presented architecture (see Fig. 2), is based on the International Data Spaces (IDS) connector specification,² which provides the interfaces needed for secure data exchange between the data owners/data providers and data users/data consumers in the RDS. The data space connector manages access control, enforces security policies, and ensures compliance with usage policies defined in contractual agreements (specified by the data owners/data providers).

3.5.1. Eclipse data space components (EDC) framework

To demonstrate the applicability of these concepts the RDS has been developed as part of Europe's Rail FP1 MOTIONAL project to test use cases (see list of public deliverables³), related to automated rail planning and operation. In the RDS, as previously stated the Eclipse Data Space components (EDC) framework was utilized (Eclipse Foundation, 2025a).

EDC is an open-source solution that deploys the latest IDS protocol (IDSA, 2025), to develop data spaces. The EDC separates the contracting metadata for exchange processing (control plane) from the data to be shared (data plane) (Neubauer et al., 2023). The architecture of the RDS is based on the Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) Minimum Viable Dataspace (MVD) (Eclipse Foundation, 2025b).

Accordingly, the EDC incorporates the latest IDS protocol in mediating data asset transfers in the RDS (IDSA, 2025). Additionally, the exploitation of EDC guarantees that data owners/data providers retain full control and autonomy over their data (Vogt et al., 2024). The application of RDS for secure and resilient digital twins presents an innovation towards establishing a standardized technical infrastructure ensuring self-sovereign data exchange, enhancing the scalability of intelligent rail services. This approach not only demonstrates the practical applicability for automated rail transport planning and operation but also builds on the efforts for a wider adoption of dataspace enabling interoperability and data integration in a secure and sovereign manner.

3.5.2. Policy enforcement

The presented architecture employs policy enforcement in the RDS that comprises of restrictions that governs the duration of data usage by data users/data consumers, the rights to view and use data, and the conditions under which the data asset can be shared or processed. Furthermore, policy enforcement within RDS incorporates measures such as rules on access rights, data usage duration, and conditions for processing or sharing of data (Nardone et al., 2024). The policies are initiated as rules to ensure that all data handling within the RDS to support the development of digital twins adheres to agreed-upon legal, ethical and standards, enabling a trusted and secure environment for all participants (Coppolino et al., 2024). In the RDS, the EDC based connector enforced real time policies that support the operationalization of the presented architecture. It handles policy enforcement at the protocol level by using baseline security policies via refining access controls, authentication protocols, and data encryption (Coppolino et al., 2024).

3.5.3. Usage control

Usage control describes how the data asset is to be handled after it has been shared by the data owners/ data producers (HaBe et al., 2020). Usage control reduces malicious data exploitation thereby protecting confidential information (Martella et al., 2025). The RDS employs Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) that supports usage control, ensuring data usage constraints applied according to usage licenses and other pre-defined conditions. The ODRL describes content usage, including prohibited, authorized, and mandatory actions, along with resources and additional information like regulations and responsibilities (Palumbo et al., 2024). Additionally, in the RDS verifiable credentials (Sporny et al., 2025), are also deployed which helps to ensure transparency, provenance, and reliability for data ownership. This ensures safe data transfer across different digital twins maintaining control over access and usage. Additionally, in the presented architecture usage

² <https://industrial-data-space.github.io/trusted-connector-documentation/>

³ <https://rail-research.europa.eu/pages/fp1-motional/deliverables>

Fig. 2. Data space architectural concept for secure and resilient digital twin.

control is implemented as a prerequisite that ensures secure data sharing and fostering trust within the RDS.

3.5.4. Transport protocols

In the RDS the connectors deploy underlying transport protocols (e.g., IDSCPv2, Data space Protocol (DSP)), to support secure point-to-point communication. For example, the interoperability of the connectors is enabled by the DSP. Where the DSP offers a set of specifications provided to enable interoperable data sharing among entities, governed by usage control and enabled by web technologies (Palumbo et al., 2024). In the RDS the DSP specifies the protocols, schemas, and communication interfaces needed for data owners/data producers to publish data, for data users/data consumers to negotiate usage agreements, and access data. In the presented architecture the DSP is important as it ensures secure data exchange and technical interoperability, facilitates different stakeholders to share data seamlessly while maintaining autonomy and control over how their data is used. DSP also enhances data trust and decreases risks associated with data sharing in the RDS. Likewise, as suggested by the IDS the Industrial Data Space Communication Protocol (IDSCP) is also deployed to encrypt data sharing between connectors employing Secure Web Sockets (WSS) (Alonso et al., 2018).

3.5.5. Identity management

As mentioned in the literature (Gan et al., 2021), identity management is deployed within the presented architecture for managing the identity information of all participants within the RDS. The RDS implements trust management via Identity and Access Management (IAM) as recommended by IDS (IDSA, 2019, 2022), for access control related decisions that are based on reliable identities and properties of participants identification (i.e., claiming an identity), authentication (i.e., verifying an identity), and authorization (i.e., making access decisions based on an identity). Moreover, based on the IDS (IDSA, 2019, 2022), the Identity Provider enables the inclusion of Certificate Authorities (CAs) who are responsible for issue and manage technical identity claims, the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) who provides short-lived tokens with up-to-date information about connectors

This also involves the Participant Information Service (ParIS) who provides business-related information of IDS Participants in machine- and human-readable manners for digital twins and other railway

systems. Thus, via IAM the connectors manage data flows for digital twins, or the integration with existing railway systems for signaling and control systems (e.g., ETCS, ERTMS). In addition, each participant of the RDS (e.g., railway operators, infrastructure managers, suppliers, manufacturers, etc.), either as data owner/data producer or data user/data consumer are supplied with an Identity Hub that administers identity management, ensuring that data exchange within the RDS is secure and that only authorized entities participate in the RDS. The EDC connector ensures that all data transactions follow the IDSA standards for data privacy, security, and sovereignty.

Each EDC connector provides services for the data owner/data producer to publish their data assets to Catalog and for the data user/data consumer to discover (via the meta data broker) (IDSA, 2022), and utilize these published data assets (Lam et al., 2025). Thereafter the federated catalog offers an aggregated catalog for all participants within the RDS by periodically collecting the registries from the local catalogs and combining all data into a local cache, aiding the discovery of data assets (via the meta data broker), across the RDS. The RDS participants can host their own data assets in external data sink and make their endpoints available for sharing data via the EDC connector. This creates a unified and reliable architecture (as seen in Fig. 2), for managing and leveraging RDS to improve the twin digital capabilities for trackside IoT devices, onboard sensors, or interlocking systems.

4. Discussion

This article examines how data spaces can enable data sharing for secure and resilient digital twins for automated rail planning and operation. Within the presented architecture, data from the physical assets (e.g. sensors, smart appliances, IoT devices, etc.), provides real-time data from railway infrastructures and assets. These physical assets generate large volumes of data that need to be securely collected, managed, and exchanged. Incorporating IoT devices into RDS involves ensuring that real time data from these devices are collected, processed, and exchanged securely, maintaining data sovereignty and trust among railway stakeholders (Nardone et al., 2024). Findings from this study highlight the potential of digital twins as the cornerstone of automated and resilient rail systems, with data spaces functioning as the essential highlighting infrastructure that unlocks their full potential.

A data space architectural concept was developed in this study to

enable secure and resilient digital twin as seen in Fig. 2 that enables the flow of real time data from the physical asset (physical equipment) to the digital asset (digital twin) and vice versa. As mentioned in the literature (Alhazmi et al., 2025; Azzedin et al., 2026; Kumar et al., 2026) digital twins are digital enablers that act as a central enabler for achieving secure, resilient, and sovereign data sharing in automated rail transportation planning and operation. Findings from this study further propose foundational work that collectively offer the architectural rigor and stakeholder-centric metrics necessary to operationalize the sovereign data-sharing principles of the Rail Data Space (RDS) within a federated twin environment.

Evidence from this study provides capabilities (modeling and automated verification of dynamic behaviors and state transitions) essential for ensuring the reliability and correctness of automated rail operations and support the RDS's goal of establishing trustworthy interactions among stakeholders by enabling dynamic assessment of digital twin behavior and safe recovery from anomalies. Results from prior studies (Alhazmi et al., 2025; Azzedin et al., 2026; Kumar et al., 2026) are analogous with findings from this current study substantiating and supporting the applicability of digital twins not merely as passive models to be used by infrastructural managers and assets managers for intelligent asset management towards automated rail transport planning and operation. But as rigorous, verifiable, and trust-aware systems that, when underpinned by sovereign data spaces, form a robust foundation for resilient and automated rail transport.

5. Conclusion

This article discusses how the federated rail data space implemented as part of Europe's Rail FP1 MOTIONAL project is leveraged for developing digital twin data representation of rail operations. Data spaces enabled digital twins provide an end-to-end exchange of real time data that could be utilized to continuously automate rail planning and operations in a secure, reliable, trusted and sovereign manner. This study proposes an architectural concept that serves as a technological building block for high-quality and effective digital model implementations to support advanced rail planning and operational processes. In conclusion, the architectural concept ensures secure, self-sovereign data exchange, enhancing the scalability and resilience of digital twins of railway services. The findings not only show the practical applicability of data space for automated rail planning and operations but also build on the efforts for a broader deployment of data spaces across the railway sector to foster collaboration. The use of data space technology contributes to resilience and secure railway systems by providing a data sharing ecosystem offering seamless real-time data access, integration, and collaborative decision-making capabilities with railway operators, infrastructure managers, suppliers, manufacturers, etc. This enhances adaptive responses to disruptions, and enhances operational agility, thereby fostering automated rail planning and operation.

5.1. Limitations and future works

In this study an architectural concept was proposed that shows how data space connectors support reliable and secure data sharing for digital twins of rail assets. The architectural concept enables the integration of RDS to facilitate the development of digital twin models that use data in real time for rail planning and operations. As with any research this study has a few limitations. First the proposed architectural concept was not yet fully validated. Secondly this study is grounded by data from the literature. Also, the connector's throughput, latency bounds, or fault-tolerance characteristics was not evaluated under realistic operational data volumes typical in rail environments such as high-frequency telemetry from trackside IoT, onboard sensors, or interlocking systems. Lastly, the architectural concept has not been tested against use cases. Therefore, future work intends to collect data from real work use cases on intelligent asset management in the railway domain. Also,

further work aims to support more diverse and complex use cases related to rail planning and operation as well as more sophisticated access control mechanisms and usage policies. The architectural concept will also be deployed as a plug-and-play model and evaluated over Docker-based virtualized infrastructure in the RDS in a cloud and on-premises environment to ensure federated data organization for automated rail transport planning and operation. Finally, the connector's throughput, latency bounds, or fault-tolerance characteristics will be evaluated based on selected IoT based use cases.

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Anthony Jnr. Bokolo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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